

COMPARISON OF ELECTRICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES BETWEEN PMN-PT AND PZT THIN FILMS IN ENERGY HARVESTER APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports the high-performance piezoelectric energy harvester (EH) fabricated with $Pb_xZr_{1-x}TiO_3$ (PZT) or $xPb(Mg_{1/3}Nb_{2/3})-(1-x)PbTiO_3$ (PMN-PT) by aerosol deposition method. The other EH with the same construction and similar thickness of PZT thin film are fabricated and used as a comparison basis. The electrical and mechanical properties of both transducers are characterized and discussed. According to our previous work [1], the output power of a EH not only depends on electrical properties, but also strongly depend on the mechanical properties of material. The mechanical properties tested by a nanoindenter shows that the Young's modulus and hardness of PMN-PT are 105.9 GPa and 4.5 GPa comparing with 86.6 GPa and 3.0 GPa of PZT, respectively. Moreover, the parameters fitting from the equivalent circuit models around resonance are $198.671 N \cdot m^{-1}$ and $174.569 N \cdot m^{-1}$ for the stiffness coefficient (K) of PMN-PT and PZT. The damping ratio (η_m) were calculated with result of $0.014 N \cdot s \cdot m^{-1}$ and $0.0155 N \cdot s \cdot m^{-1}$, respectively. The PMN-PT material has higher piezoelectric constant and lower damping which can enhance the power output. However, PMN-PT materials also have higher Young's modulus and hardness, which will lead to smaller strain when the same design of EH transducers driven under same vibration levels. From the final testing results, PMN-PT based EH devices still outperformed PZT based devices for almost twice of power output.

1. Introduction

In past years, scavenge energy from environment to power wireless sensors or other electronic devices without batteries has very high demands, especially for the coming Internet of Things (IoT) era [2]. Among all energy harvesting technologies, to harvest power from vibration with piezoelectric energy harvesters is promising because ceramic type piezoelectric materials have very high energy density, high reliability and easy to fabricated, and have been developed widely. Many researchers are concerned about the output performance of energy harvesters and working on enhanced the output power from different aspects, like materials, transducer design, fabrication processes, and even the interfacing circuitry. Gang Tang *et al.* applied phosphor bronze bonding in micro generator which can work at low frequency and high acceleration [3]. Lin *et al.* fabricated micro piezoelectric energy harvester on

stainless-steel substrate and fabricate the EH with very high output power [4]. However the output performance of EH has gradually reached the limit with PZT material. Many researchers try to enhance the performance by optimizing the design of transducer or improving the fabrication process. The other alternative is to improve the material properties with better piezoelectric performance, and lead magnesium niobate–lead titanate (PMN-PT) is one of the candidate material. PMN-PT can be epitaxial grown as single crystal piezoelectric material and will have very high piezoelectric constant and electromechanical coupling factor compared with PZT. However, with the difficulties of surface micro machining on single crystal PMN-PT, it was usually attached on substrate then polished into considerable thickness [5-7]. And the natural frequency of PMN-PT is hard to fit with ambient frequency owing to the polishing limitation [2, 8].

In order to overcome the limitation of single crystal piezoelectric material, we use aerosol deposition method to fabricate high quality thick film. Although the process cannot grow single crystal PMN-PT, the poly crystalline PMN-PT still has much better piezoelectric performance compared with PZT. With the comparison of devices fabricated with PMN-PT and PZT with exact the same geometry dimension, the output voltage, output power and power density of the PMN-PT device outperformed the PZT device performance [1]. PMN-PT has better than piezoelectric constant and the results of these comparisons are expected. However, mechanical properties, e.g., mass, damping, stiffness, play an important role in the design of energy harvester. However, PMN-PT has higher Young's modulus and hardness, and the PMN-PT device will in general has higher stiffness and has less strain under same level of excitation. If the transducer is not well designed, the advantage from higher piezoelectric performance will be cancelled in a poor transducer design. In this study, mechanical properties, hardness and Young's modulus of PMN-PT films are measured. Furthermore, by fitting the equivalent circuit model parameter from impedance measurement, the mechanical properties around resonance mode can be derived for the EH [9, 10]. The measurement results of the two materials and devices fabricated with two materials will be detailed in this study.

2. Device and Experimental Setup

Figure 1 shows the schematic illustration of our piezoelectric energy harvester device [1]. Between those comparison devices, similar thickness of PMN-PT and PZT thin film was deposited on the stainless steel by aerosol deposition as the active layers. The poling electric field is treated at 1.5 times of their own coercive field. The annealing temperature is chosen at 600 °C limited by anti-oxidation stainless steel.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the piezoelectric energy harvester device.

For measuring the output performance and the displacement of mechanical properties, a schematic diagram of experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2. In order to compare the output performance of two EHs, the thickness of PMN-PT and PZT are kept closed as 2.8 μm and 2.67 μm , respectively. The EH was mounted on the shaker which was driven by a function generator through a power amplifier to simulate ambient vibration sources with different frequency and amplitude. An accelerometer (B&K Type 4381) is fixed on the shaker with the piezoelectric EH to measure the base excitation acceleration level. Laser displacement sensor (KEYENCE LK-H150) is placed near by the shaker detecting the displacement of the tip of the cantilever beam and are calibrated in each measuring cycle.

The mechanical properties of the piezoelectric films, including Young's modulus and hardness are tested with the nanoindenter (TI 950 TriboIndenterTM).

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of experimental setup.

3. Results and Discussion

Fig. 3 shows the comparison of output voltage under an open-circuit condition in different acceleration between PMN-PT and PZT based devices. The results indicate that the PMN-PT based

device has higher output voltage than the PZT base device. The output power is calculated as,

$$P = (V_{p-p}/2\sqrt{2})^2/R \quad (1)$$

, where V_{p-p} is the peak-to-peak output voltage, and R is the load resistance. Fig 4(a)(b) shows the relationship between output voltage and output power at different resistive loads for PMN-PT and PZT based devices at 0.5g acceleration, respectively. When excited at a 0.5g acceleration level, the PMN-PT based EH could provide 8.42 μW output power which is significantly greater than the PZT based EH with 4.65 μW output power.

Moreover, the mechanical parameters fitting from the equivalent circuit models with some basic parameters are 169.8 $\text{N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ and 165.3 $\text{N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ for the stiffness coefficient (K) of PMN-PT and PZT. The damping ratio (η_m) were calculated with result of 0.0061 $\text{N}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ and 0.00711 $\text{N}\cdot\text{s}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$, respectively. And the effective piezoelectric constant (θ) of PMN-PT based device is 139 $\mu\text{N}\cdot\text{V}^{-1}$ is a little lower than 147 $\mu\text{N}\cdot\text{V}^{-1}$ of PZT based device. Corresponding to the other mechanical properties measured by the nanoindenter, Fig. 5 shows the comparison of Young's modulus and hardness of PMN-PT and PZT piezoelectric layers. The detected depth of measurement is 200 nm and the Young's modulus and hardness of PMN-PT are 105.9 GPa and 4.5 GPa comparing with 86.6 GPa and 3.0 GPa of PZT, respectively. The results of the tip displacement in resonant frequency with different acceleration under open circuit condition of PMN-PT and PZT based devices are shown in Fig. 6. From the measurement results, the PZT based device has larger displacement than PMN-PT based device. From the mechanical properties measured, we can see the PMN-PT based devices although has higher piezoelectric constants and lower damping ratio, higher Young's modulus and hardness leads to a stiffer structure and causing higher resonant frequency, lower tip displacement for the exact same dimension of cantilever beam structure.

Figure 3: Comparison of output voltage in different acceleration under open circuit condition.

Figure 4: (a) PMN-PT (b) PZT device electrical output vs. load impedance at 0.5g acceleration.

Figure 5: Comparison of Young's modulus and hardness by contacting measurement.

Figure 6: Comparison of tip displacement and resonant frequency in different acceleration level under the open circuit.

Material		PMN-PT	PZT
Thickness	[μm]	2.8	2.67
Resonant frequency	[Hz]	97.7	91.6
ε	–	413.69	455.08
d_{33}	[pC/N]	42.9	18.3
FOM (d_{33}^2/ε)	[10^{-24}C/N^2]	0.8273	0.400
Voltage(with load)@0.5g	[V_{p-p}]	1.491	1.108
Power(with load)@0.5g	[μW]	8.423	4.651
Power density@0.5g	[$\mu\text{W/mm}^3$]	82.99	48.05

Table 1: Dimension and output performance of PMN-PT and PZT device

Material		PMN-PT	PZT
C_p	[nF]	54	56
f_{sc}	[Hz]	97.4	91.3
f_{oc}	[Hz]	97.7	91.6
k_e	–	0.087	0.093
ω_n	[$\text{rad}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	611.674	573.372
M	[g]	0.531	0.531
ζ_m	–	0.0215	0.0254
V_{source}	[V]	5.3	1.8
R^*	[k Ω]	171.402	181.898
L^*	[kH]	6.517	6.245
C^*	[pF]	410.14	487.08
K	[N/m]	198.671	174.569
Θ	[C/m]	0.000285	0.000292
η_m	[N·s/m]	0.014	0.0155
V_{oc}	[V_{p-p}]	2.04	1.47
P	[μW]	8.42	4.65

Table 2: Comparison of PMN-PT and PZT based device by equivalent circuit parameters fitting.

4. Conclusions

The mechanical characteristics of PMN-PT and PZT based device are listed in Table 1, and the parameters fitting by the equivalent circuit model are listed in Table 2. With the same geometry

dimension of fabricated EH devices, the output voltage, output power and the power density of PMN-PT based devices outperformed the PZT based devices. By using different measuring methods to discuss the relevance between electrical output performance and mechanical properties of PMN-PT and PZT materials and fabricated devices, the results show that PMN-PT based devices although have higher piezoelectric constants and lower damping ratio, higher Young's modulus and hardness leads to stiffer beam and causing higher resonant frequency, lower tip displacement for the exact same dimension of cantilever beam structure. To optimize the EH transducer design based on PMN-PT materials, the mechanical properties should be taken into consideration to maximize the overall performance.

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